

**A QUALITATIVE META-ANALYSIS OF CONTEMPORARY RESEARCH
CORRELATING POST-QUANTUM VULNERABILITIES AND OPPORTUNITIES
TO CYBERSECURITY**

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Quantum computing is an emerging technology predicted to impact current and post-quantum cybersecurity, both negatively and positively. The comprehensive consequences created by quantum computing are still disturbingly indiscriminate. The lack of emerging technology elements and determinants that contributes to consequences can have unforeseen effects on research innovations, commercial applications, and national security. This study attempts to clarify current fundamental information about quantum computing, analyze prevailing quantum-based security research, and evaluate the efficacy of proposed innovations impacting cybersecurity. Our study involved retrospective analysis of research data to agnostically explore implications of post-quantum security to provide a current synopsis of research emphasis and applications, with attention on security characterizations and challenges. We then delineated research involving quantum-enhanced and quantum-affected security, cryptography, AI, blockchain, machine learning, IoT implementations, technology dependencies, and policy implications. Then we identified research and implementation gaps critically affecting the technology and policy dependencies previously identified. These gaps stimulated ancillary research that correspondingly created supplementary findings involving nation state conflicts and cyber warfare concerns. Subsequently, we concentrated on how we predict cybersecurity will impact the imminent and distant future of affected quantum and quantum affected technologies. Our research revealed that while quantum computing proposes computational advances beyond classical computing, these same innovations and implementations inhibit effectual policy and standards policy development. Current policy and standards are lacking and conflicting. Resultingly, in this study we propose a novel approach to unify and standardize research emphasis, commercial applications, and governmental policy that is crucial towards safeguarding national security and promote increased industry involvement.